

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Genetics of seedling elongation in rice

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We studied the inheritance of seedling elongation ability in an F_2 population of Pankaj/Nageribao under deepwater conditions during the 1977 wet season at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. F_2 30-day-old seedlings and parental lines raised in shallow pans were submerged in 80 cm water. Seedling height was recorded after 10 d. The frequency distributions of F_2 s and parents are presented in the table.

Frequency distribution of parents and F_2 for seedling elongation in Pankaj/Nageribao. Cuttack, India, 1977.

Plant height (cm)	Frequency distribution		F_2
	Parents		
	Pankaj	Nageribao	
0-10	—	—	—
10-20	—	—	2
20-30	—	—	6
30-40	—	—	4
40-50	—	—	5
50-60	3	—	17
60-70	19	—	26
70-80	8	—	46
80-90	—	2	70
90-100	—	8	99
100-110	—	16	97
110-120	—	3	61
120-130	—	1	11
130-140	—	—	2
Range (cm)	54.0-78.2	89.4-120.7	
Average	67.2	110.4	

In 446 F_2 plants, 270 were 90-140 cm tall, with elongation rates equal to that of the Nageribao parent; 60 plants showed poor elongation (10-70 cm), comparable to Pankaj; and 116 were intermediate (70-90 cm), elongation ability better than that of Pankaj but not equal to that of Nageribao.

The data are consistent with two dominant complementary genes for elongation ability. Presence of both genes (*Sel 1* and *Sel 2*) gave elongation ability like that of the Nageribao parent. Absence of either of the genes resulted in segregants with intermediate elongation ability; absence of both resulted in plants like the Pankaj parent. □

Breeding methods

Use of Purple Puttu rice variety as a pollen barrier in CMS line seed production

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We assessed the distance of pollen dispersal across lines of Purple Puttu 90 d after sowing, which coincides with anthesis in the CMS lines now available at the Coimbatore Paddy Breeding Station. Purple Puttu has long duration (150 d) and is highly photoperiod sensitive (120 d to flowering in the wet season, does not flower in the dry).

Glass slides smeared with vaseline and acetocarmine-glycerine were tied at 60 cm high to bamboo stakes between six rows (15 × 10-cm spacing) of Purple Puttu. One gram fresh anthers collected at 0800 h from a number of varieties were bulked and kept in closed muslin cloth bags in a petri dish under

sunlight to 1000 h. The petri dishes were placed 15 cm from the first stake at the level of the glass slides and the muslin cloth removed to allow anther sacs and pollen grains to disperse by natural wind velocity (7.2 km/h to a height of 3 m). Three such dispersals were made.

The slides were collected and the number of anther sacs and pollen grains per square inch counted. Where there were no plants of Purple Puttu in front of the slide, anther sacs averaged 2.33 and pollen grains 12.66. After the first row of Purple Puttu, anther sacs averaged 1.66 and pollen grains 6.33 per square inch; after the second row, there

Rice pollen dispersal^a with Purple Puttu as a pollen barrier.

Purple Puttu row number	Av for 3 applications	
	Anthers/inch ²	Pollen/inch ²
0 row	2.33	12.66
Row 1	1.66	6.33
Row 2	—	0.33
Row 3	—	0.33
Row 4	—	—
Row 5	—	—

^a Wind velocity at 3 m = 7.2 km/h.

were no anther sacs, and pollen grains averaged 0.33 (see table).

At least 3 lines of Purple Puttu at 15 × 10-cm or closer spacing around CMS line seed production plots can effectively intercept pollen and anther sac dispersal between different cytotsterile lines. An added advantage is that Purple Puttu's purple foliage distinguishes it from other varieties. □

Inbreeding depression of yield in rice hybrids

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Seven IRRI medium-duration hybrids (130-140 d) were tested in 1986 wet season as F_1 (3 replications) and in 1987 dry season as F_2 (4 replications) for inbreeding depression of grain yield. Grain yields in the F_2 ranged from -28.59 to 3.62% compared to the F_1 (see table). The same F_1 and F_2 were

compared with standard variety CO 43. Inbreeding depression ranged from -30.69 to -0.43%. Hybrids

IR54752A/ IR19392-2 11-1 and IR54752A/ IR4422-480-2-3-3 had yield stability in the F₂, with low inbreeding

depression (-0.43 and -0.58%, respectively). Their standard heteroses were not significant. □

Inbreeding depression (ID) of grain yield in hybrid rice.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1986-87.

Hybrid, variety	F ₁ yield	Standard	F ₂ yield	Standard	ID	F ₁ yield	F ₂ yield	ID over
	(t/ha)	heterosis	(t/ha)	heterosis		over	over	
	1986 WS	(%)	1987 DS	(%)	(%)	standard	standard	(%)
						1986 WS	1987 DS	(%)
IR46828A/IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	4.5	-29.0	3.9	-40.8	-14.0	71.0	59.2	-16.6
IR46830A/IR13292-5-3	4.5	-29.0	4.5	-32.1	- 1.4	71.0	67.9	- 4.3
IR54752A/IR54	6.0	- 6.4	4.8	-26.2	-18.8	93.6	73.8	-21.1
IR54752A/IR14753-120-3	7.0	+10.6	5.6	-14.8	-20.6	110.6	85.2	-23.0
IR54752A/IR19392-211-1	6.4	+ 0.4	6.2	- 0.1	- 2.5	100.4	100.0	- 0.4
IR54752A/IR4422-480-2-3-3	4.2	-34.2	4.4	-33.8	+ 3.6	65.8	66.2	- 0.6
IR54752A/IR20933-68-28-1-2	5.5	-14.1	3.9	-40.5	-28.6	85.9	59.5	-30.7
CO 43 (standard)	6.4	-	6.6	-	+ 3.0	100.0	100.0	-
LSD	1.1	-	1.0	-	-	-	-	-

$$^a \text{ID} = \frac{\bar{F}_2 - \bar{F}_1}{F} \times 100$$

Micropropagation of cytotsterile rice stocks

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We have propagated cytotsterile rice stocks by regenerating plants in callus culture. The important consideration in applying *in vitro* methods for propagation is to retain the genetic integrity of the original stock. There is a risk of genetic variation in plants regenerated after an intermediate callus growth phase.

In vitro propagation of rice by inducing axillary shoots or regeneration from nodal buds ensures against the possibility of genetic variation among the regenerants.

Dehusked and surface sterilized seeds of cytotsterile stock V20A were germinated on Murashige and Skoog's (MS) medium with 50 g sucrose/liter but without auxins. Six-day-old excised seedling shoots, without radicle and endosperm, were implanted on fresh MS medium supplemented with benzyladenine (BA) at 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2 mg/liter. The cultures were maintained at 25 + 1 °C with 16 h photoperiod/d.

After 3 wk, multiple axillary shoots formed from the basal region of the implanted shoots. Axillary shoot formation was highest with 2 mg BA/liter (Table 1).

When clumps of multiple shoots were about 1 cm long, they were separated

Table 1. Multiple shoot formation of the cytotsterile stock V20A after 3 wk in culture. CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Medium ^a	Shoots implanted (no.)	Axillary shoots (no.) induced after 3 wk
MS + 0.5 mg BA	17	40
MS + 1.0 mg BA	18	58
MS + 1.5 mg BA	17	80
MS + 2.0 mg BA	16	82

^aMS basic medium with 50 g sucrose/liter.

and used as fresh implants on MS medium containing different levels of BA, kinetin (K), naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), and indolebutyric acid (IBA) (Table 2).

The number of shoots increased slightly with the addition of K to the medium. The best results were with BA. Adding NAA with BA did not promote root growth; adding IBA with BA induced weak roots. Root growth was vigorous in MS medium supplemented with NAA alone, but axillary shoots were suppressed.

These results suggest that induction of multiple axillary shoots *in vitro* is feasible for the micropropagation of valuable cytotsterile stocks. Continuous axillary shoot production is possible,

Table 2. Effect of different growth regulators in multiple shoot and root formation. CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Medium ^a	Growth regulators (mg/liter)				Shoots implanted (no.)	Axillary shoots produced (no.)	Root growth ^b
	BA	K	NAA	IBA			
MS-1	2	-	-	-	26	100	-
MS-2	-	0.5	-	-	24	37	++
MS-3	2	0.5	-	-	14	43	-
MS-4	2	-	1	-	20	68	-
MS-5	2	0.5	1	-	20	54	-
MS-6	-	0.5	1	-	18	31	++
MS-7	2	-	-	1	12	21	+
MS-8	-	-	1.5	-	12	12	+++

^aMS basic medium with 50 g sucrose/liter. ^b+ = weak, ++ = good, +++ = very good.